

Supplemental material

Organohalogenated pollutants in Argentinian postpartum women living in Salta and Ushuaia

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Figure S1. GAM plots for OCPs.

Figure S2. GAM plots for PCBs.

Figure S3. GAM plots for PBDEs.

